

The Impact Of Principals' Transformational Leadership Practices On Teacher Job Commitment In Public Senior Secondary Schools

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of principals' transformational leadership practices as predictors of teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Three research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a correlational design. The population comprised 6,174 teachers in the 311 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample size was 340 teachers. The instruments that were used for data collection in this study were two self-structured scales titled 'Principals' Transformational Leadership Practices Scale (PTLPS) and Teacher Job Commitment Scale (TJCS) developed by the researcher. The face and content validities of the instruments were determined by experts and the reliability coefficient was obtained using Cronbach Alpha method to determine the internal consistency of the instruments. The reliability coefficients are as follows: Principals' transformational leadership practices .82, intellectual stimulation .80, idealized influence .83 while Teacher Job Commitment to Secondary Education Delivery was .87. The research questions were answered using simple regression while t-test associated with simple regression was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that intellectual stimulation, idealized influence, and inspirational motivation significantly predict teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery in Rivers State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended amongst others that principals should ensure that teachers stimulate their thinking and be creative. They should encourage them to think outside the box and to think independently so as to become autonomous by suggesting ways they can carry out their tasks and duties in schools.

Keywords: Principals, Transformational Leadership, Teacher Job Commitment, Public Schools and Secondary Education.

INTRODUCTION

Education is very strategic to the progress and development of any nation. It is a veritable tool critical to the transformation of a society as without it, no nation can grow, progress and develop meaningfully in all ramifications. Education can also be regarded as the oil that drives the wheel of any given society, and a viable instrument that can change the state and condition of any country. It is nonetheless, the transmission of ideas, information, knowledge and culture from one generation to another. For any society to grow and develop, it must embrace all the tenets of education and try to improve the educational system within its territory. Education aims at training the citizens of a nation and also ensuring that they become useful to themselves, as well as their society – as stated in the National Policy on Education (NPE), of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) as its goals: to create a land full of bright opportunities for all citizens. It develops a country's economy and society; therefore, it is the milestone of a nation's historical evolution towards development.

Economic and social statuses depend to a very large extent on the education obtained by an individual, as education contributes to an individual's capability in managing the quality of life (Ahmad, 2016). The main purpose of education is to train individuals within a society, to prepare and qualify them for work in the economy as well as to integrate them into the society and teach them the values and morals of the society (Karim & Abdullah, 2012). It, therefore, contributes significantly to human capacity development. It assures the development of the person to prepare him to adopt the best approach to a problem at any given time – this is especially true of formal education. In formal education, learning is structured and organized in an educational institution at different levels. In order to contribute to personal growth and development, formal education follows a predefined curriculum that helps the learner develop values, ethics, moral principles and a sense of social responsibility, thereby making the individual understand her strengths. It is typically delivered by trained professionals at the various levels – where each level has specific goals it is set out to achieve. However, the concern of this study is the secondary level of education.

At the secondary level, the training received prepares citizens for meaningful purposes and guides and prepares them for the future. Secondary education can be simply described as the education offered to pupils after the primary education and before the tertiary stage. It prepares students for tertiary education. In Nigeria, the aim is basically to provide students for the pursuit of higher education i.e. preparing the foundation for lifelong learning and meaningful living in the society. Secondary education as the name implies, is the education offered to pupils after the primary education. It is the form of education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary stage. It is the education that students acquire before the tertiary education. Secondary education has goals and these goals are essential in determining the success and growth of the educational sector. The secondary education level is the foundation for higher manpower skills being offered in the tertiary institutions. According to the National Policy on Education (NPE) of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014), the goals of secondary education include building a free and democratic society, a just and egalitarian society, a united, strong and self-reliant nation, a great and dynamic economy and a land full of opportunities for all citizens. Secondary education prepares an individual for useful living within the society and higher education. They also provide opportunities for further education, irrespective of sex, social status, religious or ethnic background.

Teachers are crucial in facilitating secondary education, ensuring the attainment of educational goals. They help students acquire knowledge and values, and their commitment is essential for effective learning. Job commitment involves a strong sense of responsibility toward an organization's goals, leading to high performance and overall excellence. Teachers must be dedicated, professional, and diligent in their roles. Teacher job commitment, demonstrated through punctuality, well-organized lessons, and continuous improvement, is vital for effective teaching and learning. Leadership plays a key role in fostering this commitment.

Leadership involves influencing individuals or groups to achieve goals, through both formal and informal means. Principals, as school leaders, manage all school activities and ensure goals are met efficiently. Leadership in education requires competencies like transformational leadership, which brings positive changes, inspires employees to exceed expectations, and supports the development of followers into leaders. Transformational leaders are passionate and energetic, focusing on a clear vision and providing support and inspiration to their team to promote growth, loyalty, and confidence. Principals' transformational leadership involves influencing, inspiring, and encouraging employees to drive positive change. Principals set examples, convey clear visions, and foster a strong organizational culture. They support, guide, and motivate their teams to work hard and remain loyal. Transformational leadership includes intellectual stimulation, idealized influence, inspirational motivation, individualized consideration, and supportive leadership. It encourages creativity, models positive behavior, motivates with goals and rewards, and provides individualized support. This leadership style aims to inspire growth, promote loyalty, and instill confidence in group members. In this assertion, the researcher investigated whether principals' transformational leadership practices (idealized influence, inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation) could be used to predict teachers' commitment in senior secondary education delivery in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Education at the secondary level is so vital to the building of the human capacity of an economy that teachers, as staff employed in schools to teach and guide students, need to commit themselves to their job in order to guide appropriately. Invariably, the teacher's attitude to work depends on the principal's ability to lead. In job commitment, there is a positive attitude an employee has towards his/her organization. It denotes a strong feeling of responsibility. A good leadership process spurs the activities of an individual or a group towards the attainment of goals. Transformational leadership is an example of such leadership style. It is a leadership approach that causes change in individuals and social systems. A transformational leader is one who ensures positive changes in those who follow him. In secondary schools, it is expected that principals direct the affairs of teachers and also lead them accordingly in order to achieve set goals. However, this seems not to be the case in most secondary schools in Rivers State. In secondary schools in Rivers State, it appears that some teachers exhibit certain behaviours that are inimical to learning outcomes, teaching ethics and values. These include lateness to work, inadequate preparation for lessons, limited efforts to support students or improve teaching practices, lack of interest in professional development, resistance to change amongst others. These attitudes can negatively impact on the teaching-learning process, the overall school environment and ultimately, secondary education delivery. This essentially suggests that there is low level of commitment of teachers to their job. This study sought to investigate the extent to which principals' transformational leadership practices which include inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and idealized influence, predict teacher job commitment.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study examined the extent to which principals' transformational leadership practices predict teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives sought to:

1. investigate the extent to which principals' intellectual stimulation predicts teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. find out the extent to which principals' idealized influence predicts teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. determine the extent to which principals' inspirational motivation predicts teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. To what extent does principals' intellectual stimulation predict teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does principals' idealized influence predict teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does principals' inspirational motivation predict teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide this study and were tested at 0.05 significance level:

1. There is no significant prediction of principals' intellectual stimulation on teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant prediction of principals' idealized influence on teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant prediction of principals' inspirational motivation on teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Significance of the Study

This study will be of benefit to principals, teachers, students, government and researchers.

This study will serve as enlightenment to principals who are heads of schools. They will be enlightened on the benefit of transformational leadership practices and its benefits in schools. They will see the need to apply these practices effectively to teachers' activities in order to enhance their job performance. Teachers will be fully abreast on the need to cooperate with principals to initiate and maintain their leadership practices. They will become aware of the importance of their job

commitment to secondary education delivery. The study will enable them to be better informed on the essence of being dedicated to their job and working with principals for effective secondary education delivery in schools.

METHODOLOGY

The design that was adopted in this study was the correlational design. The population of this study comprised the six thousand, one hundred and seventy-four (6,174) teachers in the three hundred and eleven (311) public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The 6,174 teachers served as the respondents. The sample size of this study was 375 teachers from the population. This number was determined using the Taro Yamane Mathematical formular. This method was adopted because of the large population of teachers in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The sampling method used to draw the sample was the Multistage Sampling Technique. The instruments that were used in collecting data for this study were two scales. The first scale was titled ‘Principals’ Transformational Leadership Practices Scale’ (PTLPS) and the second one was ‘Teacher Job Commitment Scale (TJCS). The instruments were divided into two sections A and B. Section A was used to generate demographic data of the respondents. Section B of PTLPS comprised fifty (50) items, while TJCS contained 25 items assessing Teacher Job Commitment to Secondary Education Delivery. This made the total items of the two instruments seventy-five (75) in all. The items were scaled using the modified four-point Likert-type rating of Very High Extent (4 points), High Extent (3 points), Low Extent (2points), and Very Low Extent (1point). The two instruments were developed by the researcher and were modified by experts. Three experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Guidance and Counselling in University of Port Harcourt validated the instruments. Their comments and suggestions were used to modify the items to ensure that in terms of clarity of words, difficulty of vocabularies, sentence structure, and relevance of items to the work were appropriate. The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha method because the instruments had more than two response options and were in sections. The data generated were analyzed with the Cronbach Alpha statistics, using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The reliability co-efficient of the (PTLPS) and (TJCS) were calculated to be 0.82 and 0.87 respectively while the reliability co-efficient of each variable were 0.80, 0.83, 0.79, 0.81, 0.80 which showed that the instruments were high and very reliable. Direct administration and retrieval method was used to administer the research instrument. Simple regression was used to answer research questions while t-test associated with simple regression was used to test hypotheses.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does principals’ intellectual stimulation predict teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent to which Principals’ Intellectual Stimulation Predicts Teacher Job Commitment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Coefficient of determinism	Decision
1	.715 ^a	.511	.509	51.1%	high extent

Scale of Measurement

0 – 25% very low extent

26 – 50% low extent

51 – 75% high extent

76 – 100% very high extent

Data on Table 1 presents the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent principals’ intellectual stimulation predicts teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. With the model as 1, the regression scores came out as .715^a, the regression square as .511 while the adjusted regression square was .509 and the coefficient of determination remained at 51.1%. When reference is made to the scale of measurement, 51.1% falls between 51-75% (high extent). Hence, judging by the coefficient of determinism, it shows that, the extent to which principals’

intellectual stimulation predicts teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is to a high extent (51.1%).

Research Question 2: *To what extent does principals' idealized influence predict teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent to which Principals' Idealized Influence Predict Teacher Job Commitment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Coefficient of determinism	Decision
1	.795 ^a	.632	.630	63.2%	high extent

The scale of measurement of Table 1 applies

Data on Table 2 presents the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent principals' idealized influence predicts teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery in Rivers State. With the model as 1, the regression scores came out as .795^a, the regression square as .632 while the adjusted regression square was .630 and the coefficient of determination remained at 63.2%. When reference is made to the scale of measurement, 63.2% falls between 51-75% (high extent). Hence, judging by the coefficient of determinism, it shows that, the extent to which principals' idealized influence predicts teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is to a high extent (63.2%).

Research Question 3: *To what extent does principals' inspirational motivation predict teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent to which Principals' Inspirational Motivation Predicts Teacher Job Commitment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Coefficient of determinism	Decision
1	.758 ^a	.574	.572	57.4%	high extent

The scale of measurement of Table 1 applies

Data on Table 3 presents the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent principals' inspirational motivation predicts teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery in Rivers State. With the model as 1, the regression scores came out as .758^a, the regression square as .574 while the adjusted regression square was .572 and the coefficient of determination remained at 57.4%. When reference is made to the scale of measurement, 57.4% falls between 51-75% (high extent). Hence, judging by the coefficient of determinism, it shows that, the extent to which principals' inspirational motivation predicts teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is to a high extent (57.4%).

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant prediction of principals' intellectual stimulation on teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent to which Principals' Intellectual Stimulation Significantly Predicts Teacher Job Commitment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	132.951	.077	38.374	.000	
	Principals' intellectual stimulation	.104	.029	.715	3.587	.000

Data on Table 4 presents the summaries of t-test associated with simple regression on the prediction of principals' intellectual stimulation on teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery in Rivers State. The t- calculated value used in testing the hypothesis came out as 3.587, the significant

value remained 0.000 with an alpha value of 0.05. At 0.05 alpha level and t- observed value of 3.587, the value of t-test associated with simple regression was 38.374 at the significant value of 0.000 which was less than the alpha value of 0.05. This suggests a significant prediction of the independent variable (principals' intellectual stimulation) on the dependent variable (teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery). On this note, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis that, there is a significant prediction of principals' intellectual stimulation on teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant prediction of principals' idealized influence on teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: Summary of t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Principals' Idealized Influence Significantly Predicts Teacher Job Commitment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	232.539	.076		33.343	.000
1 Principals' idealized influence	.060	.029	.795	2.079	.000

Data on Table 5 presents the summaries of t-test associated with simple regression on the prediction of principals' idealized influence on teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery in Rivers State. The t- calculated value used in testing the hypothesis came out as 2.079, the significant value remained 0.000 with an alpha value of 0.05. At 0.05 alpha level and t- observed value of 2.079, the value of t-test associated with simple regression was 33.343 at the significant value of 0.000 which was less than the alpha value of 0.05. This suggests a significant prediction of the independent variable (principals' idealized influence) on the dependent variable (teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery). On this note, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis that, there is a significant prediction of principals' idealized influence on teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant prediction of principals' inspirational motivation on teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: Summary of t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Principals' Inspirational Motivation Significantly Predicts Teacher Job Commitment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	412.299	.077		29.928	.000
1 Principals' inspirational motivation	.162	.030	.758	5.332	.000

Data on Table 6 presents the summaries of t-test associated with simple regression on the prediction of principals' inspirational motivation on teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery in Rivers State. The t- calculated value used in testing the hypothesis came out as 5.332, the significant value remained 0.000 with an alpha value of 0.05. At 0.05 alpha level and t- observed value of 5.332, the value of t-test associated with simple regression was 29.928 at the significant value of 0.000

which was less than the alpha value of 0.05. This suggests a significant prediction of the independent variable (principals' inspirational motivation) on the dependent variable (teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery). On this note, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis that, there is a significant prediction of principals' inspirational motivation on teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Principals' Intellectual Stimulation and Teacher Job Commitment in Schools

The result from the responses of the teachers in the first finding of the study revealed that principals' intellectual stimulation predicted teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery by 51.1%. It showed a high extent. This finding is in agreement with Ogola, Sikalieh, and Linge, (2017) who found a positive relationship between intellectual stimulation leadership styles and employees' creativity which challenges employees and energizes them to seek novel approaches to their work. It is also in consonance with the findings of Yasin (2014) who investigated the relationship between intellectual stimulation, innovations and SMEs performance in Pakistan. This study found that intellectual stimulation may be used as a tool for the development of innovations and higher SMEs performance and this study also found a strong positive relationship of innovations to the SMEs performance.

Here, if principals adopt and practice intellectual stimulation, it would have an influence on the performance of teachers in schools. The study revealed a high extent between the intellectual stimulation of principals and the commitment of teachers as it regards the delivery of secondary education in schools in Rivers State. Gautam and Enslin (2019) did not differ in their findings that showed a significantly positive relationship between intellectual stimulation and work engagement within the South African automotive retail industry. Also, Anjali and Anand (2015) established that intellectual stimulation encourages employee organizational commitment. When principals are transformational in nature and exhibit intellectual stimulation, this would lead to teachers being encouraged to put in more work and be committed to their jobs.

Transformational leaders solicit their followers' ideas and creative solutions to problems, thereby including followers to problem solving. The intellectually stimulating leader encourages followers to try new approaches. Intellectual stimulation represents an important component of transformational leadership. Through intellectual stimulation, transformational leaders encourage followers to question their own beliefs, assumptions, and values, and, when appropriate, those of the leader, which may be outdated or inappropriate for solving current problems. This finding also agrees with the outcome of the study by Abbas, Iqbal, Waheed and Riaz (2012) which revealed that intellectual stimulation has been found to be predictive of higher levels of follower innovative work behavior.

Principals' Idealized Influence and Teacher Job Commitment in Schools

In this study, it was established that principals' idealized influence predicted teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery by 63.2%. It showed a high extent. This finding agrees with the findings of Sheehan (2020) who developed a study based on transformational leaders considering idealized influence and inspirational motivation. It was identified that idealized influence can develop collaboration among employees to perform tasks and share knowledge. Transformational Leaders emphasize the employees through idealized influence for their personal development to perform better at the workplace. Transformational leaders take care of the needs of employees; thus, employees feel important at the workplace and increase their engagement at work.

Duggal (2015) found that leaders who employ a transformative leadership style can enhance positive organizational outcomes such as employee commitment through traits such as idealized influence. The findings showed that idealized influence of principals has a high extent with the job commitment of teachers as it regards the delivery of secondary education. Idealized influence has been related to a frontrunner who has charisma, is moral and one who's able to correctly communicate his or her imaginative and prescient for the organization to which he or she subordinates. These leaders have developed public values that set them apart from the crowd and have created wonderful photos for their followers.

The respondents are of the opinion that principals in schools who are transformational set high standards for work conduct and are role models for those standards. These principals build trust in

people because those who work with them know they are committed to the common good, and their sacrifices along the way evidence the consistency of their actions with their values. It showed and revealed the high extent idealized influence has with teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery. This is in agreement with Gomes (2014) who found out that principals who exhibit idealized influence manifest strong personal values that set them apart from the rest and establish positive images for their followers. This finding tends to give strength to the outcome of the study by Okoli (2021) who found out that leaders who are strong in idealized influence are more consistent in ethical and moral behaviours than being spontaneous. Followers develop an emotional attachment and strong identity with the leaders when such leaders exhibit behavioural integrity by ensuring that their deeds and espoused values rhyme. These attributes make such leaders worthy role models to the followers who admire and trust them. In turn, followers and employees will follow suit and ensure that they are committed to their jobs effectively.

Principals' Inspirational Motivation and Teacher Job Commitment in Schools

The third finding of the study revealed that principals' inspirational motivation predicted teacher job commitment to secondary education delivery by 57.4%. It revealed a high extent. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Ndwiga (2016) that showed inspirational motivation was positively and significantly related with staff performance and significantly predicted staff performance. Ndisya (2016) did not differ in his findings when he examined the application of components of transformational leadership at Safaricom. The study found a positive relationship between inspirational motivation and staff performance. Most respondents on average agreed with the presence of motivation to accomplish organizational goals and objectives, support for team building, leader's demonstration of the tasks employees should do, and assisting employees find meaning in their work. This means that the changes in the inspirational motivation had significant changes in employee performance such that when inspirational motivation increases, there would be a similar increase in employee performance.

Through inspirational motivation, transformational leaders communicate to organizational members' value-based visions that result in enhanced value congruence between the organization and its employees. This enables followers to identify more closely with the organization's goals and objectives and an alignment of their performance to that of the organization. A correlational study by Hasija et al (2019) sought to establish the effect of inspirational motivation on employee engagement, yielding a positively strong correlation. Top, Abdullah, and Faraj (2020) found the inspirational motivation to have the strongest correlation with employees' performance compared with the other dimensions of transformational leadership.

This finding of the study also agrees with that of Barine and Minja, (2014) which found out that inspirational motivation is concerned with motivating employees to a higher level of contribution and productivity. The respondents in this study attested to the fact that exhibiting inspirational motivation by principals increases teachers' intrinsic motivation, commitment, and effort, which culminate in performance improvement. Through inspirational motivation, transformational leaders communicate to organizational members' value-based visions that result in enhanced value congruence between the organization and its employees.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that principals' transformational leadership practices (intellectual stimulation, idealized principals, influence, inspirational motivation, individualized consideration and supportive leadership) all had significant prediction on teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This implies that, the way these practices are implemented can significantly impact on the commitment of teachers to achieve the objectives of secondary education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Principals should ensure that, teachers stimulate their thinking and become creative. They should encourage them to think independently outside the box by suggesting ways to carry out tasks and duties efficiently and effectively to gain autonomy.

2. Principals should act and behave in manners that teachers will imitate and implement. They should also know that they are role models and teachers look up to them, thus exhibiting behaviours that teachers would imitate.

3. Motivation is an integral part of the school process and so principals who are leaders must motivate teachers and inspire them to do more. They should also encourage teachers by raising their consciousness, thereby eliciting their commitment to the mission and vision of the schools.

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